

The Case of Delegate Access in Microsoft Exchange

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Abstract: This article defines Delegation for a mailbox in Microsoft Exchange environment and provides methods to changes for the delegates which can easily be performed by an Exchange Administrator.

Keywords: Delegate Access, Email Service troubleshooting, Client Connectivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microsoft Exchange Server is the most common email service used by organizations on premises. The service includes mailboxes for hosted users and these users vary from standard employees to Critical Position Holders such as Managers, Vice Presidents and Executives etc. Managers and higher designated officers usually need help with management of their calendars and hence their secretaries require access to their mailboxes, specifically the Calendar folder. While Outlook provides simple method to add, remove, or modify permissions to delegates; often it is requested of an I.T. organization to make these changes from Microsoft Exchange Server. There exists no simple way such as a PowerShell command to modify or update these delegates for a mailbox other than setting only one ore removing all. In cases where a mailbox has multiple delegates or to add, update, remove one or more of the delegates, I.T. does not have the ability to do so from the backend and therefore access to the person's Outlook is required to make these changes.

Delegate Access

“Delegate Access provides the ability for others to create email messages or respond to meeting requests on your behalf. As the person granting permission, you determine the level of access that the delegate has to your folders. You can grant a delegate permission to read items in your folders or to read, create, change, and delete items. By default, when you add a delegate, the delegate has full access to your Calendar and Tasks folders. The delegate can also respond to meeting requests on your behalf.”¹

II. THINK OUTSIDE THE BOX

Remove All Delegates

The steps are to either remove one or all of the delegates of a mailbox.

1. Get the list of existing delegates on a mailbox
 - a. By using Outlook, File, Account Settings, Delegate Access button:
 - b. By running the below command in an elevated Exchange Management Shell console

Get-CalendarProcessing Mailbox_Alias /fl ResourceDelegates

ResourceDelegates:

```
{domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate1 }
```


- To remove all delegates, use the below command to null the Resource Delegates

Set-CalendarProcessing Mailbox_Alias -ResourceDelegates \$Null

- Verify that the delegates have been removed

Get-CalendarProcessing Mailbox_Alias /fl ResourceDelegates

ResourceDelegates : { }

- It is recommended to remove any other permission assigned to the delegate on the Inbox with below

Remove-MailboxFolderPermission Mailbox_Alias:\inbox -User Delegate1

Add One or More Delegates

The steps are to add one or more delegates to the existing delegation access of a mailbox.

- First, record the list of existing delegates on a mailbox. Run the below in elevated Microsoft Exchange Management console:

Get-CalendarProcessing Mailbox_Alias /fl ResourceDelegates

ResourceDelegates : { domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate1 }

- Change the type of the mailbox to Room. This is needed to add or remove others as delegates. At the end of this procedure, the mailbox will be reverted back to Regular

Set-Mailbox Mailbox_Alias -Type Room

Get-Mailbox Mailbox_Alias /fl RecipientType*

RecipientType: UserMailbox

RecipientTypeDetails: RoomMailbox

- Include the existing (Delegate1) and new delegates (Delegate2, Delegate3) and set ResourceDelegates

Set-CalendarProcessing Mailbox_Alias -ResourceDelegates Delegate1, Delegate2, Delegate3

- Change the Type back to Regular

Set-Mailbox Mailbox_Alias -Type Regular

Get-Mailbox Mailbox_Alias /fl RecipientType*

RecipientType: UserMailbox

RecipientTypeDetails: UserMailbox

- Verify the new delegates and Type of UserMailbox

Get-CalendarProcessing Mailbox_Alias /fl ResourceDelegates

ResourceDelegates:

{ domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate1, domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate2, domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate3 }

Fig. II

Remove One or More Delegates

The steps are to remove one or more delegates from the existing delegation access of a mailbox.

1. Get a list of existing delegates on a mailbox. Run the below in elevated Microsoft Exchange Management console:

Get-CalendarProcessing Mailbox_Alias /fl ResourceDelegates

```
ResourceDelegates: {domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate1,
domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate2,
domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate3}
```

2. Change the type of the mailbox to Room. This is needed to add or remove others as delegates. At the end of this procedure, the mailbox will be reverted back to Regular

Set-Mailbox Mailbox_Alias -Type Room

Get-Mailbox Mailbox_Alias /fl RecipientType*

```
RecipientType: UserMailbox
```

```
RecipientTypeDetails : RoomMailbox
```

3. Set the delegates by only including the ones who should be there

Set-CalendarProcessing Mailbox_Alias -ResourceDelegates Delegate1, Delegate4

4. Change the Type back to Regular

Set-Mailbox Mailbox_Alias -Type Regular

Get-Mailbox Mailbox_Alias /fl RecipientType*

```
RecipientType: UserMailbox
```

```
RecipientTypeDetails: UserMailbox
```

5. Verify the new delegates and Type of UserMailbox

Get-CalendarProcessing Mailbox_Alias /fl ResourceDelegates

ResourceDelegates:

{domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate1, domain.com/Organizational_Unit_Users/Delegate4}

Fig. III

III. CONCLUSION

This research paper concludes the different approach to allow Exchange Administrators to support addition and removal of “Delegate Access” to any mailbox in Microsoft Exchange landscape. The procedure mentioned in this research paper is not publicly available and hence the steps are to be tested in a lab environment before making the same changes in production. These steps do not only save time, but also effort needed to efficiently manage “Delegate Access” controls based on business needs.

REFERENCES

- [1]. What is a Delegate Mailbox? <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/what-is-a-delegate-mailbox-4aa57266-44d1-4f80-9d8b-87197b7d58b1>